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MILESTONE REPORT

PRODUCT BREAKDOWN STRUCTURE

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Abstract:

The Product Breakdown Structure (PBS) of the Future Circular Collider (FCC) is presented. The first instance of the PBS is described in its current format, and the plans to further develop the PBS in the coming months and years are outlined.

Structured document of collider elements in tabular form publicly released on Zenodo (Green, open data).

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	Name	Organisation	Date
Authored by	Ghislain Roy Frank Zimmermann	CERN CERN	23/06/2021
Edited by	Julie Hadre	CERN	30/06/2021
Reviewed by	Ilya Agapov	DESY	25/06/2021
Approved by	Michael Benedikt	CERN	30/06/2021

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1. INTRODUCTION

This document presents the Product Breakdown Structure of the Future Circular Collider (FCC). The FCC is currently in a feasibility study phase with the goal to publish a concluding report by 2025. The FCC comprises two stages, starting with a lepton collider (FCC-ee), which is followed by a hadron collider (FCC-hh).

The PBS is an information structure documenting all systems, subsystems, elements down to the parts, and all equipment needed to build and assemble the end-product in a state where it can be operated. The product considered here is the FCC facility with its two stages, from the actual construction and through to the end of its actual operation, with a focus on the first stage – the lepton collider.

2. SCOPE

2.1. CDR VERSION

At this stage of the study, several key parameters have not been firmly established yet and we are awaiting major decisions in the near future. For example, the collider footprint is largely determined by constraints linked to, *inter alia*, geology and land availability at the surface.

For the time being the PBS documents the FCC as described in the Conceptual Design Report [1,2,3].

Once the actual footprint of the collider is determined the detailed design of the accelerator will proceed, and the PBS will be completed and updated through a versioning process. Throughout the study phase and the evolution of the design, the PBS will be versioned accordingly.

2.2. FCC-ee

In view of the staging of the FCC facility, we have decided to concentrate first on the production of the PBS for the first stage, *i.e.*, for the FCC-ee facility. The FCC-hh facility will be added later.

The PBS lists all equipment needed at any stage of the process. For example, the PBS lists both the 400 MHz single-cell RF cavities and the 800 MHz multi-cell RF cavities even if both will never be installed at the same time on the collider but in different stages. In other words, the PBS is the sum over time of all equipment that will be needed for the lifecycle of the FCC-ee and not a snapshot of the facility at a given time or in a given configuration.

3. DEPTH

The PBS for such a large facility as the FCC-ee collider can be extremely complex and large, but we are trying to present it here, at the stage of the feasibility study, in a concise and clear format. We have deliberately decided not to drill down to the nuts and bolts of each and every piece of equipment, but to stop at the level of "equipment" which is loosely defined as a piece of hardware that can be identified by a name, with a set functionality and that is installed as such. For example, a 10 m long bending magnet that can be lowered and installed on the collider as a single piece of equipment will be listed here as such. Later in the project, the Work Package that will be responsible for magnets will have to build the more detailed PBS of such magnet, but here and now it is not possible to be so precise.

We have limited the tree structure to six levels in order to be able to reflect the complexity and depth of the FCC at large, while keeping the data in a manageable structure. Each node in the PBS receives a unique

identification number of the form "1.2.3.", where the number of dots (e.g., 1.2.10.15. is a valid node number) represents the level in the tree structure, here the third level. Hence a six-level numbering system is used to uniquely identify each node of the structure. For example, the node "1." is the electron positron collider itself, while the node "1.1.1.4.5.1." is a BDS, a specific kind of dispersion suppressor dipole magnet in the insertion regions of the main collider ring.

4. INFORMATION PROVIDED

The information provided for each element listed in the PBS is not strictly defined and can vary from system to system or even node to node.

At the very least we shall find the official name of the element or system. A naming convention exists at CERN that will be linked to the PBS.

The multiplicity or number of identical or similar elements that can be found in the facility, under each branch, shall also be given. For example, there can some twenty identical BDS dispersion suppressor magnets installed in the FCC-ee collider.

Several additional fields indicate the technical person responsible, the technical expert, the relevant work package and any technical information that is linked to the organization of the work within the project.

Finally, free fields can be used to provide links to existing documentation. Information linked to the interfaces, fluids, dependencies to other systems and other requirements of the equipment will be of relevance.

5. PROCESS AND OUTLOOK

5.1. TOOLS

We have reviewed a couple of tools that have been used at CERN, in the past, to document Product Breakdown Structures for other projects. These have not been deemed adequate for our current needs, however. For the next few months, we have decided to resort to collecting and organising the PBS data in a spreadsheet format. The main file will be stored on EOS in the FCC directories and is temporarily available here: <https://cernbox.cern.ch/index.php/s/ajSUL3pJ985eWaG>

The collaboration-wide public documentation of the PBS is ensured through the FCC Twiki structure, available here: <https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/FCC/FCCeePBS>

5.2. UPDATE PROCESS

After the initial release of the FCC PBS, we will setup a revision process that will ensure that any update to the structure is reviewed by the relevant stakeholders (technical responsible persons in different collaborating institutes) and approved by the project management team.

The same process document will also ensure that any major decision concerning the project is reflected in the PBS, and that the consequent and appropriate change is reviewed and approved.

5.3. OUTLOOK FOR TOOLS

As we are collecting more and more information in the coming months, the spreadsheet-based PBS will no longer be easily maintainable, and we will have to start using a database-oriented tool. Initial investigation has started, and we aim to have identified and set up a database tool for the FCC PBS by early 2022.

6. REFERENCES

- [1] The FCC Collaboration, “FCC Physics Opportunities”, Future Circular Collider Conceptual Design Report Volume 1, The European Physical Journal C volume 79, Article number: 474 (2019)
- [2] The FCC Collaboration, “FCC-ee: The Lepton Collider”, Future Circular Collider Conceptual Design Report Volume 2, The European Physical Journal Special Topics volume 228, pages261–623 (2019)
- [3] The FCC Collaboration, “FCC-hh: The Hadron Collider”, Future Circular Collider Conceptual Design Report Volume 3, The European Physical Journal Special Topics volume 22, pages755–1107 (2019)

ANNEX:

Top-level table for the FCC PBS, covering the FCC-ee stage of the project as explained in the document:

Node	Level						Comments and links
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
1.	Electron-Positron Collider						
2.	Full Energy Booster						
3.	Injectors						
4.	Transfer Lines						
5.	Underground Structures and Equipment						
6.	Surface Structures and Equipment						
7.	Physics Detectors						
8.	Enabling Facilities						
9.	Software and Control Systems						

The PBS top-level structure above starts from the highest-level description from a functional point of view. Clearly, an electron-positron collider ring is needed where both beams circulate and collide at nominal energy, but also a set of physics detectors to observe and record the collisions and characterize the physical processes of interest. The full energy booster is another ring that is used to accelerate the beams and inject them into the collider at nominal energy on a quasi-continuous basis (top-up injection scheme). The beams come into the booster from injector facilities through transfer lines. The collider and booster, as well as the Physics detectors, are located in underground infrastructures comprising a long tunnel ring, lateral extensions and larger caverns. The underground infrastructures are filled with equipment required for the collider, booster and physics detectors to operate and are also equipped with safety systems and equipment, handling equipment, transport equipment (both vertically along the shafts and horizontally in the tunnel). On the surface, at the top of the pits, surface Infrastructures take the form of buildings that host equipment required for the operation of underground facilities, including electrical substations and cooling and ventilation, cryogenics supplies, etc.

A number of Enabling Facilities are required during the project, construction and operation phases of the FCC-ee. These include R&D, Test, Assembly, Storage, Operation, Maintenance and eventually Dismantling facilities. All are not needed at all stages of the lifecycle of the FCC-ee, but all are needed at least in one stage.

Finally, important immaterial assets are required to design, build, test, operate the FCC-ee take the form of Software and Control Systems, including data acquisition and analysis. These also have to be developed and maintained which requires resources and planning.